

Motion estimation: a core problem of computer vision

- Related topics:
 - Image correspondence, image registration, image matching, image alignment, ...
- Applications
 - Video enhancement: stabilization, denoising, super resolution
 - 3D reconstruction: structure from motion (SFM)
 - Video segmentation
 - Tracking/recognition
 - Advanced video editing

Contents

- **Motion perception**
- Motion representation
- Parametric motion: Lucas-Kanade
- Dense optical flow: Horn-Schunck
- Robust estimation
- Applications (1)

Seeing motion from a static picture?

The cause of motion

- Three factors in imaging process
 - Light
 - Scene
 - Camera
- Varying either of them causes motion
 - Static camera, moving scene (surveillance)
 - Moving camera, static scene (3D capture)
 - Moving camera, moving scene (sports, movie)
 - Static camera, moving scene, moving light (time lapse)

Motion scenarios (priors)

Static camera, moving scene

Moving camera, static scene

Moving camera, moving scene

Static camera, moving scene, moving light

Motion analysis: human vs. computer

- Challenges of motion estimation
 - *Geometry*: shapeless objects
 - *Reflectance*: transparency, shadow, reflection
 - *Lighting*: fast moving light sources
 - *Sensor*: motion blur, noise
- Key: motion *representation*
 - Ideally, solve the inverse rendering problem for a video sequence
 - *Intractable!*
 - Practically, we make strong assumptions
 - *Geometry*: rigid or slow deforming objects
 - *Reflectance*: opaque, Lambertian surface
 - *Lighting*: fixed or slow changing
 - *Sensor*: no motion blur, low-noise

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Parametric motion

- Mapping: $(x_1, y_1) \rightarrow (x_2, y_2)$
 - (x_1, y_1) : point in frame 1
 - (x_2, y_2) : corresponding point in frame 2
- Global parametric motion: $(x_2, y_2) = f(x_1, y_1; \theta)$
- Forms of parametric motion
 - Translation: $\begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 + a \\ y_1 + b \end{bmatrix}$
 - Similarity: $\begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ y_2 \end{bmatrix} = s \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\alpha) & \sin(\alpha) \\ -\sin(\alpha) & \cos(\alpha) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 + a \\ y_1 + b \end{bmatrix}$
 - Affine: $\begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} ax_1 + by_1 + c \\ dx_1 + ey_1 + f \end{bmatrix}$
 - Homography: $\begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{z} \begin{bmatrix} ax_1 + by_1 + c \\ dx_1 + ey_1 + f \end{bmatrix}, z = gx_1 + hy_1 + i$

Parametric motion forms

Optical flow field

- Parametric motion is limited and cannot describe the motion of arbitrary videos
- Optical flow field: assign a flow vector $(u(x, y), v(x, y))$ to each pixel (x, y)
- Projection from 3D world to 2D

Optical flow field visualization

- Too messy to plot flow vector for every pixel
- Map flow vectors to color
 - Magnitude: saturation
 - Orientation: hue

Input two frames

Ground-truth flow field

Visualization code
[Baker et al. 2007]

Matching criterion

- Brightness constancy assumption

$$I_1(x, y) = I_2(x + u, y + v) + n$$

$$n \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$$

- **Noise** n (will revisit later)

- Matching criteria

- What's invariant between two images?
 - Brightness, gradients, phase, other features...
- Distance metric (L2, robust functions)

$$E(u, v) = \sum_{x,y} (I_1(x, y) - I_2(x + u, y + v))^2$$

- Correlation, normalized cross correlation (NCC)

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Lucas-Kanade: problem setup

- Given two images $I_1(x, y)$ and $I_2(x, y)$, estimate a parametric motion that transforms I_1 to I_2
- Let $\mathbf{x} = (x, y)^T$ be a column vector indexing pixel coordinate
- Two typical transforms

- Translation: $W(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{p}) = \begin{bmatrix} x + p_1 \\ y + p_2 \end{bmatrix}$

- Affine: $W(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{p}) = \begin{bmatrix} p_1 x + p_3 y + p_5 \\ p_2 x + p_4 y + p_6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} p_1 & p_3 & p_5 \\ p_2 & p_4 & p_6 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$

- Goal of the Lucas-Kanade algorithm

$$\mathbf{p}^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{p}} \sum_{\mathbf{x}} [I_2(W(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{p})) - I_1(\mathbf{x})]^2$$

An incremental algorithm

- Difficult to directly optimize the objective function

$$p^* = \arg \min_p \sum_x [I_2(W(x; p)) - I_1(x)]^2$$

- Instead, we try to optimize each step

$$\Delta p^* = \arg \min_{\Delta p} \sum_x [I_2(W(x; p + \Delta p)) - I_1(x)]^2$$

- The transform parameter is updated:

$$p \leftarrow p + \Delta p^*$$

Taylor expansion

- The term $I_2(W(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{p} + \Delta\mathbf{p}))$ is highly nonlinear
- Taylor expansion:

$$I_2(W(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{p} + \Delta\mathbf{p})) \approx I_2(W(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{p})) + \nabla I_2 \frac{\partial W}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \Delta\mathbf{p}$$

- $\frac{\partial W}{\partial \mathbf{p}}$: *Jacobian* of the warp
- If $W(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{p}) = \left(W_x(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{p}), W_y(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{p}) \right)^T$, then

$$\frac{\partial W}{\partial \mathbf{p}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial W_x}{\partial p_1} & \cdots & \frac{\partial W_x}{\partial p_n} \\ \frac{\partial W_y}{\partial p_1} & \cdots & \frac{\partial W_y}{\partial p_n} \end{bmatrix}$$

Gauss-Newton

- With Taylor expansion, the objective function becomes

$$\Delta \mathbf{p}^* = \arg \min_{\Delta \mathbf{p}} \sum_{\mathbf{x}} \left[I_2(W(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{p})) + \nabla I_2 \frac{\partial W}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \Delta \mathbf{p} - I_1(\mathbf{x}) \right]^2$$

Or in a vector form:

$$\Delta \mathbf{p}^* = \arg \min_{\Delta \mathbf{p}} (\mathbf{I}_t + \mathbf{B} \Delta \mathbf{p})^T (\mathbf{I}_t + \mathbf{B} \Delta \mathbf{p})$$

Where $\mathbf{B} = [\mathbf{I}_x \mathbf{X} \quad \mathbf{I}_y \mathbf{X} \quad \mathbf{I}_x \mathbf{Y} \quad \mathbf{I}_y \mathbf{Y} \quad \mathbf{I}_x \quad \mathbf{I}_y] \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 6}$

$$\mathbf{I}_t = \mathbf{I}_2(\mathbf{W}(\mathbf{p})) - \mathbf{I}_1$$

- Solution:

$$\Delta \mathbf{p}^* = -(\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{B})^{-1} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{I}_t$$

Hessian matrix

How it works

Compute matrix

$$\mathbf{B} = \left[\nabla I_2 \frac{\partial W}{\partial p} \right]$$

How it works

Compute inverse Hessian: $(\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{B})^{-1}$

$$\mathbf{B} = \left[\nabla I_2 \frac{\partial W}{\partial p} \right]$$

How it works

Compute: $\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{I}_t$

$$\mathbf{B} = \left[\nabla I_2 \frac{\partial W}{\partial p} \right]$$

How it works

Solve linear system:
 $\Delta p^* = -(\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{B})^{-1} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{I}_t$

$$\mathbf{B} = \left[\nabla I_2 \frac{\partial W}{\partial p} \right]$$

How it works

$$p \leftarrow p + \Delta p^*$$

Translation

- Jacobian: $\frac{\delta W}{\delta p} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$
- $\nabla I_2 \frac{\delta W}{\delta p} = [I_x \ I_y]$
- $\mathbf{B} = [I_x \ I_y] \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 2}$
- Solution:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta p^* &= -(\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{B})^{-1} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{I}_t \\ &= - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_x^T \mathbf{I}_x & \mathbf{I}_x^T \mathbf{I}_y \\ \mathbf{I}_x^T \mathbf{I}_y & \mathbf{I}_y^T \mathbf{I}_y \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_x^T \mathbf{I}_t \\ \mathbf{I}_y^T \mathbf{I}_t \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Coarse-to-fine refinement

- Lucas-Kanade is a greedy algorithm that converges to local minimum
- Initialization is crucial: if initialized with zero, then the underlying motion must be small
- If underlying transform is significant, then coarse-to-fine is a must

Variations

- Variations of Lucas Kanade:
 - Additive algorithm [Lucas-Kanade, 81]
 - Compositional algorithm [Shum & Szeliski, 98]
 - Inverse compositional algorithm [Baker & Matthews, 01]
 - Inverse additive algorithm [Hager & Belhumeur, 98]
- Although inverse algorithms run faster (avoiding re-computing Hessian), they have the same complexity for robust error functions!

From parametric motion to flow field

- Incremental flow update (du, dv) for pixel (x, y)

$$\begin{aligned} & I_2(x + u + du, y + v + dv) - I_1(x, y) \\ &= I_2(x + u, y + v) + I_x(x + u, y + v)du + I_y(x + u, y + v)dv - I_1(x, y) \end{aligned}$$

$$I_x du + I_y dv + I_t = 0$$

- We obtain the following function within a patch

$$\begin{bmatrix} du \\ dv \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_x^T \mathbf{I}_x & \mathbf{I}_x^T \mathbf{I}_y \\ \mathbf{I}_x^T \mathbf{I}_y & \mathbf{I}_y^T \mathbf{I}_y \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_x^T \mathbf{I}_t \\ \mathbf{I}_y^T \mathbf{I}_t \end{bmatrix}$$

- The flow vector of each pixel is updated independently
- Median filtering can be applied for spatial smoothness

Example

Input two frames

Coarse-to-fine LK

Coarse-to-fine LK with median filtering

Flow visualization

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Motion ambiguities

- When will the Lucas-Kanade algorithm fail?

$$\begin{bmatrix} du \\ dv \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_x^T \mathbf{I}_x & \mathbf{I}_x^T \mathbf{I}_y \\ \mathbf{I}_x^T \mathbf{I}_y & \mathbf{I}_y^T \mathbf{I}_y \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_x^T \mathbf{I}_t \\ \mathbf{I}_y^T \mathbf{I}_t \end{bmatrix}$$

- The inverse may not exist!!!
- How?
 - All the derivatives are zero: *flat regions*
 - X- and y-derivatives are linearly correlated: *lines*

Aperture problem

Corners

Lines

Flat regions

Dense optical flow with spatial regularity

- Local motion is inherently ambiguous
 - *Corners*: definite, no ambiguity (but can be misleading)
 - *Lines*: definite along the normal, ambiguous along the tangent
 - *Flat regions*: totally ambiguous
- Solution: imposing spatial smoothness to the flow field
 - Adjacent pixels should move together as much as possible
- Horn & Schunck equation

$$(u, v) = \arg \min \iint (I_x u + I_y v + I_t)^2 + \alpha (|\nabla u|^2 + |\nabla v|^2) dx dy$$

- $|\nabla u|^2 = \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}\right)^2 = u_x^2 + u_y^2$
- α : smoothness coefficient

How to solve a large linear system $Ax=b$?

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_x^2 + \alpha \mathbf{L} & \mathbf{I}_x \mathbf{I}_y \\ \mathbf{I}_x \mathbf{I}_y & \mathbf{I}_y^2 + \alpha \mathbf{L} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U \\ V \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_x \mathbf{I}_t \\ \mathbf{I}_y \mathbf{I}_t \end{bmatrix}$$

- With $\alpha > 0$, this system is positive definite!
- You can use your favorite iterative solver
 - Gauss-Seidel, successive over-relaxation (SOR)
 - (Pre-conditioned) conjugate gradient
- No need to wait for the solver to converge completely

Incremental Solution

- In the objective function

$$(u, v) = \arg \min \iint (I_x u + I_y v + I_t)^2 + \alpha(|\nabla u|^2 + |\nabla v|^2) dx dy$$

The displacement (u, v) has to be small for the Taylor expansion to be valid

- More practically, we can estimate the optimal incremental change

$$\iint (I_x du + I_y dv + I_t)^2 + \alpha(|\nabla(u + du)|^2 + |\nabla(v + dv)|^2) dx dy$$

- The solution becomes

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_x^2 + \alpha \mathbf{L} & \mathbf{I}_x \mathbf{I}_y \\ \mathbf{I}_x \mathbf{I}_y & \mathbf{I}_y^2 + \alpha \mathbf{L} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} dU \\ dV \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_x \mathbf{I}_t + \alpha \mathbf{L} U \\ \mathbf{I}_y \mathbf{I}_t + \alpha \mathbf{L} V \end{bmatrix}$$

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Horn-Schunck

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Video stabilization

Video denoising

Original

Denoised

Video super resolution

Low-Res

